

NARENDRA MODI

Prime Minister of India

सत्यमेव जयते

Welcome : Sardar Dilbag Singh Khalsa

- User Dashboard
- Appeal Dashboard
- Lodge Public Grievance
- Account Activity
- Edit Profile
- Change Password
- Sign out**

Grievance Details

Registration Number

PMOPG/E/2025/0053822

Name

Sardar Dilbag Singh Khalsa

Date of receipt

18/04/2025

Address

Mehtanagar Pandit deendayal upadhyay ward mehtanagar
Pandit deendayal upadhyay ward mehtanagar

State

Chhattisgarh

District

Balodabazar-Bhatapara

Mobile Number

9981240811

Email ID

sdskdilbag1994@gmail.com

Phone Number

Not Provided

Grievance Description

Financial Services (Banking Division) >> Fraud >> ATM

Bank : State Bank of India

Branch / Name of Bank and Branch : Bhatapara

Chhattisgarh 493118

Place of ATM : ATM Near Railway Station

Dear Sir , I am Sardar Dilbag Singh Khalsa, Central government and Chhattisgarh government are trying to confine me by not providing railway ticket and cash from ATM. Kindly check CCTV of all the ATM of Bhatapara and the activities in railways station. Bhatapara 493118. I have applied for VISA card , not a single otp I have received from bank. I have given some mail and they have send message in different mail. They are unnecessarily cancelling train and confining me. Mainly RSS ke *gunde*

Communication Details

Sn.	Date of Action	Action	From	To
1	18/04/2025	RECEIVED THE GRIEVANCE	You	Prime Minister's Office
2	02/05/2025	CASE DISPOSED OF	State Bank of India	You

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Information Technology (I

[← Back To Home Page](#)